

Research Article

Investigation into the Physiological Effects of Nanometer Light Energized Water Study 3: Meridian and Acupuncture Data

Caitlin A Connor^{1*}, Melinda H Connor², Jens Eickhoff³, Marsha Perry⁴ and Holly Shipione⁵

¹Green Mountain Health Care, Complimentary Medicine, Akamai University, USA

²Research Methodologist, Earthsongs Holistic Consulting, USA

³Eickhoff Statistical Consulting, USA

⁴Earthsongs Holistic Consulting, USA

⁵Green Mountain Health Care, USA

Abstract

Methods: LifeWave X2O, beakers, beaker stands, and bottled water. The Biowell and BioPulsar provided the Bioelectric-magnetic measures. Citrulline and Sulforaphane were given to the supplement group, while a placebo was given to the water only group.

Measures were taken before and after drinking the water within the same 24-hour period. A single blind study with two groups which were a randomized sample of 10 subjects each were made up of both men and women aged 40-90 with the goal of 10 subjects in each group completing the study. Since this study focused on the impact of energized water with and without supplements, 10 subjects were given a placebo at the beginning of testing and drank energized water alone in group 1 and 10 subjects were given Sulforaphane at the beginning of testing and drank the energized water with Citrulline.

Subjects were consented and demographic measures were taken. Immediately after this they were asked to take either a sul-

foraphane tableted or a placebo. Once this was done measures were taken. Participants were then wired to the Physio suite HRV and a measure was taken. Once that was done they were asked to drink the water, either with or without the citrulline mixed in - concurrent Near Infrared images taken before, while drinking, and after. Following this all of the tests were repeated in opposite order.

Results: Most of the important changes were between the two groups. All of the test measures, except the Doppler Laser Perfusion Imager, had at least one change in significance.

Conclusion: This study reinforces the previous two studies findings of broad wellness effects with a documented trend toward improved body function. A longer test period is a logical next step to see how these effects either stabilize or change over time.

Keywords: BioPulsar; BioWell; BioGraph Infinity Thought Technology Physiological Test Suite; Doppler Perfusion Imager; HRV; Interstitial Resistance; Water

Introduction

This was a discovery study to investigate the physiological effects on individuals consuming water energized by light when combined with Sulforaphane and Citrulline. The LifeWave X2O, which infuses water using focused light of specific wavelengths, was used, in combination with Sulforaphane [1] and Citrulline [2].

Background

Recent research has demonstrated the validity of research on water structure and function. Some of that research specifically supports changes in water structure based on photobiomodulation variations of light [3]. Water is vital to human life, it is critical to life functions [4], water holds cell walls together [5], water holds DNA together [5], the body is made of water [4]. This study was the third in a series, so it focused on the combined effects of the energized water with Sulforaphane and Citrulline. Sulforaphane is commonly found in cruciferous vegetables and may have health benefits, including anticancer effects [6]. Citrulline levels have been shown to correlate to how effectively the intestine is absorbing nutrients [7].

Materials

LifeWave water energizing device, beakers, beaker stands, and bottled water. Thought Technology Infinity Physiology Suite including HRV, EEG, EMG, TEMP, Galvanic Skin Response and Blood Volume Pulse. Vitals included Temp, pulse, respiration, blood pressure and O₂saturation. CO₂ measures and blood glucose were also taken. Interstitial testing included weight, kCal, BMI, % muscle, % fat, visceral fat and body age. The Biowell and BioPulsar provided the Bioelectric-magnetic measures. Yugi wetwipes were also used. Doppler Perfusion Imaging was also done. Near infrared images were taken before, during and after drinking the water concurrent with the physiology suite data. Citrulline and Sulforaphane were given to the supplement group, while a placebo was given to the water only group.

*Corresponding author: Caitlin A Connor, Green Mountain Health Care, Complimentary Medicine, Akamai University, USA, E-mail: caitlin_connor@mindspring.com

Citation: Connor CA, Connor MH, Eickhoff J, Perry M, Shipione H (2025) Investigation into the Physiological Effects of Nanometer Light Energized Water Study 3: Meridian and Acupuncture Data. HSOA J Altern Complement Integr Med 11: 573.

Received: April 04, 2025; **Accepted:** April 15, 2025; **Published:** April 22, 2025

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- **L-Citrulline**

Beyond Raw Chemistry Labs L-Citrulline Lab grade, 3 grams per serving.

- **Sulforaphane**

Carlyle Sulforaphane from broccoli seed extract contains 400 mcg free of gluten, wheat, yeast, milk, lactose, soy artificial flavor, sweetener, and nonGMO.

- **Thought Technology BioGraph Infinity Physiology Suite**

Complete Thought Technology IS7910 Biograph Infinity Physiology Suite testing including EKG, temp, galvanic skin response, blood volume pulse, respiration and EMG measures were taken. CardioPro SA7597 Infinity HRV analysis software was used to analyze measures.

Three 3 minute measures were taken: prior, during and post drinking the energized water. Analysis was done with CardioPro software and measures panel was loaded into spread sheets for additional statistical analysis.

- **Bio-Well**

Bio-Well 3.0, with 3.0 Bio-Well software.

- **BioPulsar**

BioPulsar-Reflexograph by Auramed version 4 meets medical device act test specifications CE 0483 and EMC test specifications directive 89/336/EEC with brass 24 carat gold plated sensors. With version 4.9 BioPulsar software.

- **Doppler Perfusion Imaging**

Perimed AB PIM II Laser Doppler Perfusion Imager with LISCA Opto-I Isolation Unit.

- **Near Infrared Photos**

FLIR One Pro LT iOS Pro-Grade thermal camera for smart phones. High resolution IR images with 1440 by 1080 visual resolution and 80 by 60 thermal resolution accuracy is +/-3C or +/-5% when unit is within 15C to 35C. And scene is within 5C to 120C.

- **Omron Body Composition and Weight Scale (2021)**

Made by Omron Healthcare in 2021, the HBF-514C Body Composition and Weight Scale has seven measures available: Body fat %, Body Mass Index, Skeletal Muscle, Resting Metabolism, Visceral fat, Body age, weight. Measures for this study include original weight, body fat and body age.

- **Vitals**

The following vitals measures were taken including Pulse Oximeter, Blood Pressure (Sphygmomanometer Manual Arm Blood Pressure Monitor BP Cuff Gauge tester Machine), temperature and respiration.

- **CO2 measures**

Contec CO2 Capnograph mainstream respiration rate End-Tidal and Portable air quality monitor 400-5000 PPM mini CO2 detector.

- **Blood Glucose**

TRUMATRIX meter starter kit with TRUMATRIX test strips.

Methods

Ethics approval was NAOEP/IJHC 03-30-24-2. Measures were taken before and after drinking the water within the same 24-hour period. Two groups which were a randomized sample of 10 subjects each were made up of both men and women aged 40-90 with the goal of 10 subjects in each group completing the study. Once all 20 subjects had completed the study recruiting and consenting was stopped. Since this study focused on the impact of energized water, 10 subjects were given a placebo at the beginning of testing and drank energized water alone in group 1 and 10 subjects were given Sulforaphane at the beginning of testing and drank the energized water with Citrulline.

Subjects were consented and demographic measures were taken. Immediately after this they were asked to take either a sulforaphane tableted or a placebo. Once this was done Weight with interstitial age, and Base temp, blood pressure, O₂ sat, glucose and CO₂ were taken. After that Biowell/GDV, then BioPulsar, and Doppler Perfusion Imaging were also done. Participants were then wired to the Physio suite HRV and a measure was taken. Once that was done they were asked to drink the water, either with or without the citrulline mixed in - concurrent Near Infrared images taken before, while drinking, and after. Following this all of the tests were repeated in opposite order.

Statistics

Demographic variables were summarized using frequencies and percentages or mean and standard deviation, stratified by study group. Physio suite HRV outcome parameters were summarized in terms of medians, stratified by study group and assessment timepoint (pre vs. post). Changes of physio suite HRV outcome parameters within groups from the pre- to post assessments were evaluated using a non-parametric Wilcoxon signed rank test. Comparisons of changes from the pre- to post assessments of physio suite HRV parameters between study groups were conducted using a nonparametric Wilcoxon rank sum test. All other outcome measures were summarized in terms of means and standard deviation, stratified by study arm and assessment time point. Changes in those outcome measures within groups from the pre- to post assessments were evaluated using a paired t-test while comparisons of changes from the pre- to post assessments between study groups were conducted using a two-sample t-test. The intent-to-treat population was used as the primary analysis population. All reported P-values are two-sided and P<0.05 was used to define statistical significance.

Results

Demographics

The age range for this study was 40-79, with the average age being 71. The population was ¼ men and the rest were women.

Biowell

The Biowell provided the information and areas of statistical relevance as follows (Tables 1-11)

Parameter	Finger	Name	p-value
Area	L Ring Finger	2. Nervous system	0.054
Area	L Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	0.036
Area	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.012
Area	R Fore Finger	6. Blind gut	0.034
Area	R Fore Finger	Whole image	0.055
Area	R Middle Finger	1. Thorax zone, Respiratory system	0.068
Area	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	0.042
Area	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	0.094
Area	R Thumb Finger	Whole image	0.068
Area (C),	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	0.06
Area (C),	L Ring Finger	2. Nervous system	0.025
Area (C),	L Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	0.085
Area (C),	L Thumb Finger	2. Right ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	0.097
Area (C),	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.015
Area (C),	R Fore Finger	6. Blind gut	0.04
Area (C),	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	0.058
Area (C),	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	0.06
Area (C),	R Thumb Finger	Whole image	0.08
Norm area	L Ring Finger	1. Hypothalamus	0.081
Norm area	L Ring Finger	3. Spleen	0.099
Norm area	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	0.094
Norm area	L Ring Finger	8. Pituitary gland	0.014
Norm area	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	0.042
Norm area	L Ring Finger	Whole image	0.046
Norm area	L Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	0.089
Norm area	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.068
Norm area	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	0.035
Intensity	L Little Finger	4. Jejunum	0.089
Intensity	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	0.02
Intensity	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	0.05
Inner area	L Ring Finger	1. Hypothalamus	0.047
Inner area	L Ring Finger	3. Spleen	0.075
Inner area	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	0.04
Inner area	L Ring Finger	5. Adrenal	0.012
Inner area	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	0.016
Inner area	L Ring Finger	7. Thyroid gland	0.071
Inner area	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	0.029
Inner area	L Ring Finger	Whole image	0.027
Inner area	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	0.09

Table 1: Water 3 Biowell Comparisons of Changes between Groups.

Parameter	Finger	Name	p-value
Inner noise	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.039
Inner noise	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	0.056
Inner noise	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	0.091
Inner noise	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	0.006
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	1. Hypothalamus	0.021
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	5. Adrenal	0.056
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	7. Thyroid gland	0.055
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	8. Pituitary gland	0.038
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	0.018
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	Whole image	0.035
Inner noise (%)	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.054
Inner noise (%)	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	0.006
Inner noise (%)	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	0.099
Inner noise (%)	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	0.014
Inner noise (%)	R Ring Finger	6. Spleen	0.069
Inner noise (%)	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	0.084
Inner noise (%)	R Ring Finger	8. Hypothalamus	0.064
Inner noise (%)	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	0.068
Energy	L Ring Finger	2. Nervous system	0.049
Energy	L Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	0.03
Energy	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.017
Energy	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	0.086
Energy	R Fore Finger	6. Blind gut	0.028
Energy	R Fore Finger	Whole image	0.092
Energy	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	0.072
Energy	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	0.091
Energy (C),	L Ring Finger	2. Nervous system	0.034
Energy (C),	L Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	0.026
Energy (C),	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.016
Energy (C),	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	0.08
Energy (C),	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	0.095
Energy (C),	R Fore Finger	6. Blind gut	0.035
Energy (C),	R Fore Finger	Whole image	0.092
Energy (C),	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	0.08
Energy (C),	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	0.099

Table 2: Water 3 Biowell Comparisons of Changes between Groups.

Parameter	Finger	Name	p-value
FC	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum, Prostate	0.074
FC	L Fore Finger	6. Spine - lumbar zone	0.089
FC	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	0.048
FC	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	0.02
FC	L Middle Finger	Whole image	0.008
FC	L Ring Finger	1. Hypothalamus	0.042

FC	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	0.021
FC	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.097
FC	R Ring Finger	6. Spleen	0.022
FC	R Ring Finger	8. Hypothalamus	0.054
FC	R Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	0.099
EC	L Fore Finger	6. Spine - lumbar zone	0.065
EC	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	0.036
EC	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	0.015
EC	L Middle Finger	Whole image	0.009
EC	L Ring Finger	1. Hypothalamus	0.02
EC	L Ring Finger	3. Spleen	0.045
EC	L Ring Finger	5. Adrenal	0.055
EC	L Ring Finger	8. Pituitary gland	0.076
EC	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	0.01
EC	L Ring Finger	Whole image	0.012
EC	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.073
EC	L Thumb Finger	7. Left eye	0.089
EC	R Fore Finger	3. Spine - lumbar zone	0.045
EC	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum, Prostate	0.035
EC	R Fore Finger	Whole image	0.095
EC	R Ring Finger	6. Spleen	0.009
EC	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	0.003
Inner contour length	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	0.086
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	1. Hypothalamus	0.066
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	3. Spleen	0.022
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	0.087
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	5. Adrenal	0.016
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	0.059
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	7. Thyroid gland	0.011
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	8. Pituitary gland	0.036
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	0.018
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	Whole image	0.012
Inner contour length	R Ring Finger	3. Pancreas	0.05
Inner contour length	R Ring Finger	6. Spleen	0.086
Inner contour length	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	0.044

Table 3: Water 3 Biowell Comparisons of Changes between Groups.

Parameter	Finger	Name	p-value
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	1. Hypothalamus	0.023
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	3. Spleen	0.047
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	0.053
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	5. Adrenal	0.013
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	0.009
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	7. Thyroid gland	0.098
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	8. Pituitary gland	0.078
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	0.034
Inner contour radius	L Ring Finger	Whole image	0.031
Inner contour radius	R Ring Finger	8. Hypothalamus	0.083
Outer contour length	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	0.078
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	0.056
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	Whole image	0.045
Outer contour length	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	0.081
Outer contour length	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	0.03
Outer contour length	L Thumb Finger	7. Left eye	0.034
Outer contour length	R Ring Finger	6. Spleen	0.084
Outer contour length	R Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	0.045
Outer contour radius	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	0.043
Outer contour radius	L Ring Finger	5. Adrenal	0.012
Outer contour radius	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	0.013
Outer contour radius	L Ring Finger	7. Thyroid gland	0.093
Outer contour radius	L Ring Finger	Whole image	0.079
Outer contour radius	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	0.049
Outer contour radius	R Little Finger	5. Heart	0.071
Outer contour radius	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	0.011
Outer contour radius	R Ring Finger	8. Hypothalamus	0.082

Table 4: Water 3 Biowell Comparisons of Changes between Groups.

Parameter	Finger	Name	Time	p-value
Area	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Pre	
Area	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Post	
Area	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Change Pre-Post	0.023
Area	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Pre	
Area	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Post	
Area	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Change Pre-Post	0.015
Area	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Pre	
Area	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Post	
Area	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Change Pre-Post	0.056
Area (C),	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Pre	
Area (C),	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Post	
Area (C),	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Change Pre-Post	0.038

Area (C),	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Pre	
Area (C),	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Post	
Area (C),	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Change Pre-Post	0.057
Area (C),	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Pre	
Area (C),	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Post	
Area (C),	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Change Pre-Post	0.021
Area (C),	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Pre	
Area (C),	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Post	
Area (C),	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Change Pre-Post	0.047
Norm area	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Pre	
Norm area	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Post	
Norm area	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Change Pre-Post	0.018
Norm area	L Little Finger	6. Coronary vessels	Pre	
Norm area	L Little Finger	6. Coronary vessels	Post	
Norm area	L Little Finger	6. Coronary vessels	Change Pre-Post	0.026
Norm area	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Pre	
Norm area	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Post	
Norm area	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Change Pre-Post	0.056

Table 5: Water 3 Biowell Supplement group.

Parameter	Finger	Name	Time	p-value
Intensity	L Fore Finger	9. Transverse colon	Pre	
Intensity	L Fore Finger	9. Transverse colon	Post	
Intensity	L Fore Finger	9. Transverse colon	Change Pre-Post	0.022
Intensity	L Little Finger	1. Left part of heart	Pre	
Intensity	L Little Finger	1. Left part of heart	Post	
Intensity	L Little Finger	1. Left part of heart	Change Pre-Post	0.039
Intensity	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Pre	
Intensity	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Post	
Intensity	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Change Pre-Post	0.049
Intensity	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Pre	
Intensity	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Post	
Intensity	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Change Pre-Post	0.053
Intensity	R Middle Finger	2. Immune system	Pre	

Intensity	R Middle Finger	2. Immune system	Post	
Intensity	R Middle Finger	2. Immune system	Change Pre-Post	0.053
Intensity	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Pre	
Intensity	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Post	
Intensity	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Change Pre-Post	0.031
Inner area	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Pre	
Inner area	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Post	
Inner area	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Change Pre-Post	0.039
Inner area	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Pre	
Inner area	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Post	
Inner area	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Change Pre-Post	0.052
Inner area	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	Pre	
Inner area	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	Post	
Inner area	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	Change Pre-Post	0.012
Inner area	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Pre	
Inner area	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Post	
Inner area	R Fore Finger	5. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Change Pre-Post	0.035
Inner area	R Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	Pre	
Inner area	R Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	Post	
Inner area	R Thumb Finger	1. Right eye	Change Pre-Post	0.053

Table 6: Water 3 Biowell Supplement group.

Parameter	Finger	Name	Time	p-value
Inner noise	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Pre	
Inner noise	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Post	
Inner noise	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Change Pre-Post	0.047
Inner noise	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Pre	
Inner noise	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Post	
Inner noise	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Change Pre-Post	0.033
Inner noise	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Pre	
Inner noise	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Post	
Inner noise	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Change Pre-Post	0.018
Inner noise	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Pre	

Inner noise	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Post	
Inner noise	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Change Pre-Post	0.003
Inner noise	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Pre	
Inner noise	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Post	
Inner noise	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Change Pre-Post	0.044
Inner noise (%)	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Pre	
Inner noise (%)	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Post	
Inner noise (%)	L Fore Finger	3. Rectum	Change Pre-Post	0.018
Inner noise (%)	L Little Finger	1. Left part of heart	Pre	
Inner noise (%)	L Little Finger	1. Left part of heart	Post	
Inner noise (%)	L Little Finger	1. Left part of heart	Change Pre-Post	0.042
Inner noise (%)	L Little Finger	2. Left kidney	Pre	
Inner noise (%)	L Little Finger	2. Left kidney	Post	
Inner noise (%)	L Little Finger	2. Left kidney	Change Pre-Post	0.008
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	Pre	
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	Post	
Inner noise (%)	L Ring Finger	9. Epiphysis	Change Pre-Post	0.044
Inner noise (%)	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Pre	
Inner noise (%)	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Post	
Inner noise (%)	L Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Change Pre-Post	0.02
Inner noise (%)	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Pre	
Inner noise (%)	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Post	
Inner noise (%)	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Change Pre-Post	0.047
Inner noise (%)	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Pre	
Inner noise (%)	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Post	
Inner noise (%)	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Change Pre-Post	0.024

Table 7: Water 3 Biowell Supplement group.

Parameter	Finger	Name	Time	p-value
Energy	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Pre	
Energy	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Post	
Energy	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Change Pre-Post	0.03
Energy	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Pre	
Energy	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Post	
Energy	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Change Pre-Post	0.014
Energy	R Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Pre	
Energy	R Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Post	
Energy	R Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Change Pre-Post	0.009
Energy	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Pre	
Energy	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Post	
Energy	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Change Pre-Post	0.019
Energy (C),	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Pre	
Energy (C),	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Post	
Energy (C),	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Change Pre-Post	0.029
Energy (C),	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Pre	
Energy (C),	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Post	
Energy (C),	L Thumb Finger	3. Jaw, Teeth right side	Change Pre-Post	0.015
Energy (C),	R Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Pre	
Energy (C),	R Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Post	
Energy (C),	R Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Change Pre-Post	0.009
Energy (C),	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Pre	
Energy (C),	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Post	
Energy (C),	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Change Pre-Post	0.017
FC	L Fore Finger	6. Spine - lumbar zone	Pre	
FC	L Fore Finger	6. Spine - lumbar zone	Post	

FC	L Fore Finger	6. Spine - lumbar zone	Change Pre-Post	0.032
FC	L Little Finger	5. Right part of heart	Pre	
FC	L Little Finger	5. Right part of heart	Post	
FC	L Little Finger	5. Right part of heart	Change Pre-Post	0.04
FC	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Pre	
FC	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Post	
FC	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Change Pre-Post	0.029
FC	L Middle Finger	Whole image	Pre	
FC	L Middle Finger	Whole image	Post	
FC	L Middle Finger	Whole image	Change Pre-Post	0.009
FC	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	Pre	
FC	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	Post	
FC	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	Change Pre-Post	0.046

Table 8: Water 3 Biowell Supplement group.

Parameter	Finger	Name	Time	p-value
FC	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Pre	
FC	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Post	
FC	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Change Pre-Post	0.015
FC	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Pre	
FC	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Post	
FC	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Change Pre-Post	0.059
EC	L Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Pre	
EC	L Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Post	
EC	L Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Change Pre-Post	0.058
EC	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Pre	
EC	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Post	
EC	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Change Pre-Post	0.046
EC	L Ring Finger	8. Pituitary gland	Pre	
EC	L Ring Finger	8. Pituitary gland	Post	

EC	L Ring Finger	8. Pituitary gland	Change Pre-Post	0.058
EC	R Ring Finger	6. Spleen	Pre	
EC	R Ring Finger	6. Spleen	Post	
EC	R Ring Finger	6. Spleen	Change Pre-Post	0.038
EC	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	Pre	
EC	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	Post	
EC	R Ring Finger	7. Nervous system	Change Pre-Post	0.01
EC	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Pre	
EC	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Post	
EC	R Thumb Finger	8. Cerebral zone (cortex)	Change Pre-Post	0.007
Inner contour length	L Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Pre	
Inner contour length	L Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Post	
Inner contour length	L Little Finger	3. Mammary glands, Respiratory system	Change Pre-Post	0.044
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	7. Thyroid gland	Pre	
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	7. Thyroid gland	Post	
Inner contour length	L Ring Finger	7. Thyroid gland	Change Pre-Post	0.01

Table 9: Water 3 Biowell Supplement group.

Parameter	Finger	Name	Time	p-value
Inner contour radius	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Pre	
Inner contour radius	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Post	
Inner contour radius	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone	Change Pre-Post	0.044
Inner contour radius	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Pre	
Inner contour radius	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Post	
Inner contour radius	L Fore Finger	5. Sacrum	Change Pre-Post	0.037
Inner contour radius	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	Pre	
Inner contour radius	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	Post	
Inner contour radius	R Fore Finger	4. Sacrum	Change Pre-Post	0.032

Inner contour radius	R Thumb Finger	2. Right ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Pre	
Inner contour radius	R Thumb Finger	2. Right ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Post	
Inner contour radius	R Thumb Finger	2. Right ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Change Pre-Post	0.047
Inner contour radius	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Pre	
Inner contour radius	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Post	
Inner contour radius	R Thumb Finger	6. Left ear, Nose, Maxillary sinus	Change Pre-Post	0.033
Outer contour length	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone, Prostate	Pre	
Outer contour length	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone, Prostate	Post	
Outer contour length	L Fore Finger	4. Coccyx, Pelvis minor zone, Prostate	Change Pre-Post	0.039
Outer contour length	L Little Finger	5. Right part of heart	Pre	
Outer contour length	L Little Finger	5. Right part of heart	Post	
Outer contour length	L Little Finger	5. Right part of heart	Change Pre-Post	0.052

Table 10: Water 3 Biowell Supplement group.

Parameter	Finger	Name	Time	p-value
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Pre	
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Post	
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	2. Left kidney	Change Pre-Post	0.036
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Pre	
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Post	
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	7. Cerebral zone (vessels)	Change Pre-Post	0.055
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	Whole image	Pre	
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	Whole image	Post	
Outer contour length	L Middle Finger	Whole image	Change Pre-Post	0.021
Outer contour length	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	Pre	
Outer contour length	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	Post	
Outer contour length	L Ring Finger	4. Urogenital system	Change Pre-Post	0.014
Outer contour length	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Pre	

Outer contour length	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Post	
Outer contour length	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Change Pre-Post	0.024
Outer contour length	L Thumb Finger	7. Left eye	Pre	
Outer contour length	L Thumb Finger	7. Left eye	Post	
Outer contour length	L Thumb Finger	7. Left eye	Change Pre-Post	0.051
Outer contour length	R Little Finger	2. Ileum	Pre	
Outer contour length	R Little Finger	2. Ileum	Post	
Outer contour length	R Little Finger	2. Ileum	Change Pre-Post	0.045
Outer contour length	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Pre	
Outer contour length	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Post	
Outer contour length	R Thumb Finger	5. Jaw, Teeth left side	Change Pre-Post	0.04
Outer contour radius	L Fore Finger	1. Descending colon	Pre	
Outer contour radius	L Fore Finger	1. Descending colon	Post	
Outer contour radius	L Fore Finger	1. Descending colon	Change Pre-Post	0.035
Outer contour radius	L Little Finger	4. Jejunum	Pre	
Outer contour radius	L Little Finger	4. Jejunum	Post	
Outer contour radius	L Little Finger	4. Jejunum	Change Pre-Post	0.023
Outer contour radius	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Pre	
Outer contour radius	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Post	
Outer contour radius	L Ring Finger	6. Pancreas	Change Pre-Post	0.054
Outer contour radius	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Pre	
Outer contour radius	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Post	
Outer contour radius	R Ring Finger	4. Adrenal	Change Pre-Post	0.047

Table 11: Water 3 Biowell Supplement group.

BioPulsar

The BioPulsar provided the information and areas of statistical relevance as follows (Tables 12-27)

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Nose	30 seconds	Pre	3.41	3.18	
Nose	30 seconds	Post	6.75	1.02	

Nose	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	3.34	3.17	0.009
Nose	60 seconds	Pre	3.76	3.25	
Nose	60 seconds	Post	6.26	2.07	
Nose	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	2.5	3.31	0.041
Nose	90 seconds	Pre	4.32	3.17	
Nose	90 seconds	Post	5.33	2.52	
Nose	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	1.02	3.78	0.418
Nose	End	Pre	5.25	2.52	
Nose	End	Post	5.35	2.69	
Nose	End	Change Pre-Post	0.1	2.68	0.913
Esophagus	30 seconds	Pre	1.78	2.27	
Esophagus	30 seconds	Post	3.42	3.46	
Esophagus	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	1.63	2.68	0.086
Esophagus	60 seconds	Pre	1.72	2.32	
Esophagus	60 seconds	Post	3.34	3.38	
Esophagus	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	1.62	2.65	0.084
Esophagus	90 seconds	Pre	1.17	1.82	
Esophagus	90 seconds	Post	2.39	3.05	
Esophagus	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	1.21	3.82	0.343
Esophagus	End	Pre	0.94	1.29	
Esophagus	End	Post	2.34	2.97	
Esophagus	End	Change Pre-Post	1.4	2.57	0.118
Lung	30 seconds	Pre	6.72	2.29	
Lung	30 seconds	Post	6.71	1.96	
Lung	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.01	2.94	0.995
Lung	60 seconds	Pre	5.4	3.02	
Lung	60 seconds	Post	7.21	0.96	
Lung	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	1.81	2.57	0.054
Lung	90 seconds	Pre	5.44	3.44	
Lung	90 seconds	Post	7.23	0.67	
Lung	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	1.79	3.51	0.142
Lung	End	Pre	5.36	3.37	
Lung	End	Post	7.3	0.94	
Lung	End	Change Pre-Post	1.94	3.37	0.102

Table 12: Water 3 Biopulsar Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Heart	30 seconds	Pre	7.49	0.66	
Heart	30 seconds	Post	7	0.83	
Heart	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.49	1.12	0.202
Heart	60 seconds	Pre	7.56	0.96	
Heart	60 seconds	Post	6.54	2.28	
Heart	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.02	2.87	0.29
Heart	90 seconds	Pre	7.44	0.74	
Heart	90 seconds	Post	5.69	2.8	
Heart	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.75	2.74	0.074
Heart	End	Pre	7.4	0.79	
Heart	End	Post	5.85	2.96	
Heart	End	Change Pre-Post	-1.55	2.92	0.127
Duodenum	30 seconds	Pre	7.05	2.41	
Duodenum	30 seconds	Post	6.13	3.05	
Duodenum	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.92	2.68	0.307
Duodenum	60 seconds	Pre	7.05	2.42	
Duodenum	60 seconds	Post	6.11	3.05	
Duodenum	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.93	2.6	0.286
Duodenum	90 seconds	Pre	6.7	3.19	
Duodenum	90 seconds	Post	6.34	3.21	
Duodenum	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.36	0.49	0.044
Duodenum	End	Pre	6.91	2.31	
Duodenum	End	Post	5.86	3.51	
Duodenum	End	Change Pre-Post	-1.05	2.78	0.262
Small Intestine	30 seconds	Pre	6.09	2.85	
Small Intestine	30 seconds	Post	5.22	2.7	
Small Intestine	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.87	1.16	0.043
Small Intestine	60 seconds	Pre	6.77	2.36	
Small Intestine	60 seconds	Post	5.43	2.7	
Small Intestine	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.34	2.27	0.095
Small Intestine	90 seconds	Pre	6.67	2.27	
Small Intestine	90 seconds	Post	6.45	2.22	
Small Intestine	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.23	3.59	0.847

Small Intestine	End	Pre	6.61	2.24	
Small Intestine	End	Post	5.75	2.67	
Small Intestine	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.86	2.11	0.23

Table 13: Water 3 Biopulsar Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	30 seconds	Pre	8.25	0.48	
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	30 seconds	Post	7.49	1.09	
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.76	1.35	0.108
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	60 seconds	Pre	8.44	0.6	
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	60 seconds	Post	7.75	1.11	
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.69	1.26	0.118
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	90 seconds	Pre	8.53	0.93	
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	90 seconds	Post	8.03	1.38	
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.5	0.72	0.055
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	End	Pre	8.23	1.13	
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	End	Post	7.82	2.06	
Large Intestine, Sigmoidum	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.41	1.27	0.329
Urethra	30 seconds	Pre	7.69	0.58	
Urethra	30 seconds	Post	6.83	1.19	
Urethra	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.86	1.5	0.104
Urethra	60 seconds	Pre	6.85	2.21	
Urethra	60 seconds	Post	6.91	1.02	
Urethra	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.06	2.37	0.941
Urethra	90 seconds	Pre	7.41	1.2	
Urethra	90 seconds	Post	6.53	1.3	
Urethra	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.89	1.32	0.062
Urethra	End	Pre	7.1	1.47	
Urethra	End	Post	6.51	1.44	
Urethra	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.59	1.54	0.258

Table 14: Water 3 Biopulsar Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Kidney	30 seconds	Pre	6.72	0.6	
Kidney	30 seconds	Post	4.24	3.23	
Kidney	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-2.49	3.42	0.047
Kidney	60 seconds	Pre	6.16	1.78	
Kidney	60 seconds	Post	5.24	2.65	
Kidney	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.92	3.65	0.447
Kidney	90 seconds	Pre	6.9	0.77	
Kidney	90 seconds	Post	5.88	1.79	
Kidney	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.02	1.38	0.045
Kidney	End	Pre	7.01	0.59	
Kidney	End	Post	6.15	1.84	
Kidney	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.86	1.78	0.16
Adrenal Gland	30 seconds	Pre	7.17	0.4	
Adrenal Gland	30 seconds	Post	6.4	2.08	
Adrenal Gland	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.77	2	0.254
Adrenal Gland	60 seconds	Pre	5.85	2.74	
Adrenal Gland	60 seconds	Post	6.19	2.19	
Adrenal Gland	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.34	2.36	0.656
Adrenal Gland	90 seconds	Pre	6.73	2.13	
Adrenal Gland	90 seconds	Post	5.64	2.68	
Adrenal Gland	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.09	2.2	0.15
Adrenal Gland	End	Pre	7.38	0.37	
Adrenal Gland	End	Post	5.33	3	
Adrenal Gland	End	Change Pre-Post	-2.06	3.06	0.062
Feet	30 seconds	Pre	7.25	1.13	
Feet	30 seconds	Post	6.99	1.07	
Feet	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.26	0.43	0.084
Feet	60 seconds	Pre	7.33	1.44	
Feet	60 seconds	Post	6.86	1.08	
Feet	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.47	0.69	0.059
Feet	90 seconds	Pre	7.09	1.32	
Feet	90 seconds	Post	6.89	0.97	
Feet	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.2	0.87	0.486

Feet	End	Pre	7.04	1.6	
Feet	End	Post	7.03	0.99	
Feet	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.01	1.54	0.992

Table 15: Water 3 Biopulsar Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	30 seconds	Pre	6.97	0.38	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	30 seconds	Post	6.6	1.16	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.37	0.98	0.269
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	60 seconds	Pre	6.95	0.58	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	60 seconds	Post	6.59	0.84	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.37	0.59	0.079
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	90 seconds	Pre	6.96	1.02	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	90 seconds	Post	6.63	0.85	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.33	0.6	0.12
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	End	Pre	6.84	0.94	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	End	Post	6.57	0.85	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.27	0.62	0.207

Table 16: Water 3 Biopulsar Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	30 seconds	Pre	1.18	1.89	
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	30 seconds	Post	2.5	2.65	
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	1.32	2.37	0.111
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	60 seconds	Pre	0.98	1.26	
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	60 seconds	Post	2.44	2.67	
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	1.46	2.38	0.084
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	90 seconds	Pre	1.32	1.69	
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	90 seconds	Post	1.47	2.31	
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.15	2.74	0.866

Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	End	Pre	1.07	1.63	
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	End	Post	1.89	2.42	
Cerebrum, Mesencephalon	End	Change Pre-Post	0.82	2.58	0.341
Temporal Brain	30 seconds	Pre	7.35	1.02	
Temporal Brain	30 seconds	Post	7.29	0.47	
Temporal Brain	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.06	1.24	0.876
Temporal Brain	60 seconds	Pre	7.21	1.04	
Temporal Brain	60 seconds	Post	7.25	0.5	
Temporal Brain	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.04	1.16	0.916
Temporal Brain	90 seconds	Pre	7.23	1.2	
Temporal Brain	90 seconds	Post	7.52	0.58	
Temporal Brain	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.29	1.08	0.411
Temporal Brain	End	Pre	7.22	1.18	
Temporal Brain	End	Post	7.84	0.73	
Temporal Brain	End	Change Pre-Post	0.61	1	0.083

Table 17: Water 3 Biopulsar no Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Thyroid	30 seconds	Pre	7.69	0.56	
Thyroid	30 seconds	Post	7.29	0.38	
Thyroid	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.4	0.36	0.007
Thyroid	60 seconds	Pre	7.52	0.63	
Thyroid	60 seconds	Post	6.95	0.83	
Thyroid	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.57	1.14	0.146
Thyroid	90 seconds	Pre	7.34	0.88	
Thyroid	90 seconds	Post	6.94	0.63	
Thyroid	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.39	1.06	0.271
Thyroid	End	Pre	7.32	1.16	
Thyroid	End	Post	6.96	0.8	
Thyroid	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.36	1.09	0.324
Shoulder	30 seconds	Pre	5.61	2.22	
Shoulder	30 seconds	Post	5.19	2.18	
Shoulder	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.42	1.39	0.37
Shoulder	60 seconds	Pre	5.72	2.1	
Shoulder	60 seconds	Post	4.86	2.47	
Shoulder	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.87	1.97	0.197

Shoulder	90 seconds	Pre	5.83	2.08	
Shoulder	90 seconds	Post	4.86	2.47	
Shoulder	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.98	2.07	0.17
Shoulder	End	Pre	5.82	2.27	
Shoulder	End	Post	4.19	2.84	
Shoulder	End	Change Pre-Post	-1.63	2.78	0.097
Lung	30 seconds	Pre	6.84	1.36	
Lung	30 seconds	Post	5.93	2.22	
Lung	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.92	2.09	0.197
Lung	60 seconds	Pre	6.81	1.4	
Lung	60 seconds	Post	5.56	2.78	
Lung	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.25	2.09	0.091
Lung	90 seconds	Pre	6.78	1.65	
Lung	90 seconds	Post	5.58	2.79	
Lung	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.2	2.15	0.112
Lung	End	Pre	6.73	2.27	
Lung	End	Post	5.32	2.81	
Lung	End	Change Pre-Post	-1.41	2.3	0.083

Table 18: Water 3 Biopulsar no Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Heart	30 seconds	Pre	7.6	0.88	
Heart	30 seconds	Post	6.44	2.15	
Heart	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.17	2.08	0.11
Heart	60 seconds	Pre	7.55	0.88	
Heart	60 seconds	Post	6.32	2.12	
Heart	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.24	2.19	0.108
Heart	90 seconds	Pre	7.64	0.94	
Heart	90 seconds	Post	5.81	2.88	
Heart	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-1.84	3.54	0.135
Heart	End	Pre	7.68	0.7	
Heart	End	Post	5.69	2.72	
Heart	End	Change Pre-Post	-1.99	3.11	0.074
Stomach	30 seconds	Pre	6.8	1.27	
Stomach	30 seconds	Post	6.91	0.38	
Stomach	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.11	1.16	0.769
Stomach	60 seconds	Pre	6.79	0.99	

Stomach	60 seconds	Post	6.77	0.52	
Stomach	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.03	0.94	0.932
Stomach	90 seconds	Pre	7.15	0.42	
Stomach	90 seconds	Post	6.55	1.19	
Stomach	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.6	1.19	0.145
Stomach	End	Pre	7.32	0.47	
Stomach	End	Post	6.8	0.65	
Stomach	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.52	0.61	0.024
Pancreas	30 seconds	Pre	7.84	0.59	
Pancreas	30 seconds	Post	7.5	0.57	
Pancreas	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.35	0.34	0.011
Pancreas	60 seconds	Pre	7.86	0.62	
Pancreas	60 seconds	Post	7.47	0.54	
Pancreas	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.39	0.27	0.001
Pancreas	90 seconds	Pre	8.01	0.7	
Pancreas	90 seconds	Post	7.59	0.6	
Pancreas	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.42	0.5	0.027
Pancreas	End	Pre	8.09	0.88	
Pancreas	End	Post	7.41	0.83	
Pancreas	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.68	1.05	0.07

Table 19: Water 3 Biopulsar no Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Spleen	30 seconds	Pre	6.85	1.17	
Spleen	30 seconds	Post	6.73	0.7	
Spleen	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.12	0.66	0.585
Spleen	60 seconds	Pre	6.8	1.2	
Spleen	60 seconds	Post	6.32	1.39	
Spleen	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.48	1.37	0.296
Spleen	90 seconds	Pre	6.86	1.25	
Spleen	90 seconds	Post	6.58	0.96	
Spleen	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.29	0.42	0.059
Spleen	End	Pre	6.94	1.31	
Spleen	End	Post	6.66	0.85	
Spleen	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.27	0.66	0.229
Duodenum	30 seconds	Pre	7.67	0.32	
Duodenum	30 seconds	Post	7.37	0.52	

Duodenum	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.3	0.57	0.129
Duodenum	60 seconds	Pre	7.79	0.38	
Duodenum	60 seconds	Post	7.09	1.24	
Duodenum	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.71	1.13	0.08
Duodenum	90 seconds	Pre	7.91	0.65	
Duodenum	90 seconds	Post	7.5	0.46	
Duodenum	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.41	0.64	0.07
Duodenum	End	Pre	8	0.75	
Duodenum	End	Post	6.66	2.23	
Duodenum	End	Change Pre-Post	-1.34	2.63	0.141
Small Intestine	30 seconds	Pre	6.97	2.14	
Small Intestine	30 seconds	Post	7.07	0.64	
Small Intestine	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.11	1.74	0.849
Small Intestine	60 seconds	Pre	7.05	1.55	
Small Intestine	60 seconds	Post	7.05	0.75	
Small Intestine	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.01	1.27	0.99
Small Intestine	90 seconds	Pre	7.45	0.61	
Small Intestine	90 seconds	Post	7.13	0.58	
Small Intestine	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.32	0.39	0.031
Small Intestine	End	Pre	7.53	0.46	
Small Intestine	End	Post	7.18	0.75	
Small Intestine	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.35	0.73	0.165

Table 20: Water 3 Biopulsar no Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Descending Colon	30 seconds	Pre	7.18	0.9	
Descending Colon	30 seconds	Post	6.94	0.48	
Descending Colon	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.24	0.78	0.353
Descending Colon	60 seconds	Pre	7.03	0.9	
Descending Colon	60 seconds	Post	6.84	0.51	
Descending Colon	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.19	0.74	0.429

Descending Colon	90 seconds	Pre	7.03	0.91	
Descending Colon	90 seconds	Post	6.61	0.69	
Descending Colon	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.41	0.61	0.06
Descending Colon	End	Pre	7.05	0.98	
Descending Colon	End	Post	6.66	0.84	
Descending Colon	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.39	0.93	0.219
Kidney	30 seconds	Pre	6.14	1.92	
Kidney	30 seconds	Post	6.59	0.64	
Kidney	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.45	1.96	0.489
Kidney	60 seconds	Pre	6.06	1.94	
Kidney	60 seconds	Post	6.4	0.66	
Kidney	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.34	2.03	0.612
Kidney	90 seconds	Pre	6.69	0.61	
Kidney	90 seconds	Post	6.29	0.71	
Kidney	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.4	0.36	0.006
Kidney	End	Pre	6.75	0.59	
Kidney	End	Post	6.23	0.96	
Kidney	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.52	0.88	0.092
Bladder	30 seconds	Pre	7.46	0.53	
Bladder	30 seconds	Post	7	0.48	
Bladder	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.47	0.42	0.006
Bladder	60 seconds	Pre	7.3	0.49	
Bladder	60 seconds	Post	6.87	0.51	
Bladder	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.43	0.36	0.005
Bladder	90 seconds	Pre	7.08	0.66	
Bladder	90 seconds	Post	6.57	0.52	
Bladder	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.52	0.66	0.036
Bladder	End	Pre	6.93	0.82	
Bladder	End	Post	6.53	0.67	
Bladder	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.4	1	0.244

Table 21: Water 3 Biopulsar no Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Adrenal Gland	30 seconds	Pre	5.9	2.26	
Adrenal Gland	30 seconds	Post	6.23	1.97	

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Adrenal Gland	30 seconds	Pre	5.9	2.26	
Adrenal Gland	30 seconds	Post	6.23	1.97	
Adrenal Gland	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.32	1.36	0.47
Adrenal Gland	60 seconds	Pre	6.29	2.01	
Adrenal Gland	60 seconds	Post	5.96	1.89	
Adrenal Gland	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.33	0.53	0.084
Adrenal Gland	90 seconds	Pre	6.45	2.09	
Adrenal Gland	90 seconds	Post	5.77	1.86	
Adrenal Gland	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.69	0.61	0.006
Adrenal Gland	End	Pre	6.41	2.1	
Adrenal Gland	End	Post	5.9	1.89	
Adrenal Gland	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.51	0.5	0.01
Reproductive Organs	30 seconds	Pre	7.36	0.62	
Reproductive Organs	30 seconds	Post	7	0.49	
Reproductive Organs	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.36	0.57	0.077
Reproductive Organs	60 seconds	Pre	7.14	0.6	
Reproductive Organs	60 seconds	Post	6.82	0.47	
Reproductive Organs	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.31	0.51	0.082
Reproductive Organs	90 seconds	Pre	6.98	0.61	
Reproductive Organs	90 seconds	Post	6.48	0.64	
Reproductive Organs	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.51	0.7	0.048
Reproductive Organs	End	Pre	6.9	0.76	
Reproductive Organs	End	Post	6.49	0.82	
Reproductive Organs	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.41	1.1	0.271
Hip	30 seconds	Pre	7.67	0.71	
Hip	30 seconds	Post	7.3	0.62	
Hip	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.37	0.52	0.05
Hip	60 seconds	Pre	7.49	0.71	
Hip	60 seconds	Post	7.2	0.73	
Hip	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.29	0.42	0.056

Hip	90 seconds	Pre	7.04	0.99	
Hip	90 seconds	Post	6.67	1.05	
Hip	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.38	1	0.262
Hip	End	Pre	6.72	1.22	
Hip	End	Post	6.4	1.19	
Hip	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.32	1.23	0.431

Table 22: Water 3 Biopulsar no Supplement group.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Feet	30 seconds	Pre	7.26	0.72	
Feet	30 seconds	Post	6.77	0.99	
Feet	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.49	0.92	0.128
Feet	60 seconds	Pre	7.04	0.67	
Feet	60 seconds	Post	6.53	1.17	
Feet	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.51	0.97	0.13
Feet	90 seconds	Pre	6.75	0.98	
Feet	90 seconds	Post	6.11	1.45	
Feet	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.64	1.09	0.097
Feet	End	Pre	6.56	1.23	
Feet	End	Post	6.14	1.5	
Feet	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.42	1.24	0.312
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	30 seconds	Pre	6.93	1.29	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	30 seconds	Post	6.69	0.98	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.23	0.76	0.36
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	60 seconds	Pre	6.8	1.24	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	60 seconds	Post	6.53	1.06	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.27	0.74	0.273
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	90 seconds	Pre	6.75	1.27	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	90 seconds	Post	6.4	1.05	

Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.35	0.72	0.166
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	End	Pre	6.81	1.42	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	End	Post	6.21	1.18	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.6	0.76	0.034

Table 23: Water 3 Biopulsar no Supplement group.

Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	90 seconds	Pre	7.13	0.73	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	90 seconds	Post	6.8	0.57	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.34	0.73	0.178
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	End	Pre	7.03	0.87	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	End	Post	6.55	0.59	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.48	0.9	0.126

Table 24: Water 3 Biopulsar no Supplement group.

Parameter	Time-Point	Time	Mean	SD	p-value (change within Group)
Average Belly, Chest Area	30 seconds	Pre	6.29	0.62	
Average Belly, Chest Area	30 seconds	Post	6.21	0.49	
Average Belly, Chest Area	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.08	0.86	0.772
Average Belly, Chest Area	60 seconds	Pre	6.33	0.56	
Average Belly, Chest Area	60 seconds	Post	6.03	0.76	
Average Belly, Chest Area	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.3	0.95	0.338
Average Belly, Chest Area	90 seconds	Pre	6.46	0.54	
Average Belly, Chest Area	90 seconds	Post	5.92	0.88	
Average Belly, Chest Area	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.54	0.61	0.021
Average Belly, Chest Area	End	Pre	6.38	0.59	
Average Belly, Chest Area	End	Post	5.89	0.75	
Average Belly, Chest Area	End	Change Pre-Post	-0.49	0.74	0.064
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	30 seconds	Pre	7.37	0.43	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	30 seconds	Post	7.03	0.46	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.35	0.6	0.099
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	60 seconds	Pre	7.25	0.42	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	60 seconds	Post	6.91	0.45	
Average Lower Abdominal Area, Legs	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	-0.35	0.51	0.059

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	p-value
Nose	30 seconds	Pre	
Nose	30 seconds	Post	
Nose	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.006
Nose	60 seconds	Pre	
Nose	60 seconds	Post	
Nose	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.044
Nose	90 seconds	Pre	
Nose	90 seconds	Post	
Nose	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.423
Nose	End	Pre	
Nose	End	Post	
Nose	End	Change Pre-Post	0.821
Thyroid	30 seconds	Pre	
Thyroid	30 seconds	Post	
Thyroid	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.024
Thyroid	60 seconds	Pre	
Thyroid	60 seconds	Post	
Thyroid	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.328
Thyroid	90 seconds	Pre	
Thyroid	90 seconds	Post	
Thyroid	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.321
Thyroid	End	Pre	
Thyroid	End	Post	
Thyroid	End	Change Pre-Post	0.172
Neck	30 seconds	Pre	
Neck	30 seconds	Post	
Neck	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.727
Neck	60 seconds	Pre	

Neck	60 seconds	Post	
Neck	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.922
Neck	90 seconds	Pre	
Neck	90 seconds	Post	
Neck	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.095
Neck	End	Pre	
Neck	End	Post	
Neck	End	Change Pre-Post	0.41

Table 25: Water 3 Biopulsar Comparisons of Changes between Groups.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	p-value
Lung	30 seconds	Pre	
Lung	30 seconds	Post	
Lung	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.434
Lung	60 seconds	Pre	
Lung	60 seconds	Post	
Lung	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.009
Lung	90 seconds	Pre	
Lung	90 seconds	Post	
Lung	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.034
Lung	End	Pre	
Lung	End	Post	
Lung	End	Change Pre-Post	0.018
Thymus Gland	30 seconds	Pre	
Thymus Gland	30 seconds	Post	
Thymus Gland	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.161
Thymus Gland	60 seconds	Pre	
Thymus Gland	60 seconds	Post	
Thymus Gland	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.188
Thymus Gland	90 seconds	Pre	
Thymus Gland	90 seconds	Post	
Thymus Gland	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.376
Thymus Gland	End	Pre	
Thymus Gland	End	Post	
Thymus Gland	End	Change Pre-Post	0.083
Transverse Colon	30 seconds	Pre	
Transverse Colon	30 seconds	Post	
Transverse Colon	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.066
Transverse Colon	60 seconds	Pre	
Transverse Colon	60 seconds	Post	
Transverse Colon	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.085
Transverse Colon	90 seconds	Pre	
Transverse Colon	90 seconds	Post	

Transverse Colon	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.513
Transverse Colon	End	Pre	
Transverse Colon	End	Post	
Transverse Colon	End	Change Pre-Post	0.822

Table 26: Water 3 Biopulsar Comparisons of Changes between Groups.

Parameter	TimePoint	Time	p-value
Kidney	30 seconds	Pre	
Kidney	30 seconds	Post	
Kidney	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.03
Kidney	60 seconds	Pre	
Kidney	60 seconds	Post	
Kidney	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.354
Kidney	90 seconds	Pre	
Kidney	90 seconds	Post	
Kidney	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.193
Kidney	End	Pre	
Kidney	End	Post	
Kidney	End	Change Pre-Post	0.597
Ureter	30 seconds	Pre	
Ureter	30 seconds	Post	
Ureter	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.057
Ureter	60 seconds	Pre	
Ureter	60 seconds	Post	
Ureter	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.165
Ureter	90 seconds	Pre	
Ureter	90 seconds	Post	
Ureter	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.492
Ureter	End	Pre	
Ureter	End	Post	
Ureter	End	Change Pre-Post	0.429
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	30 seconds	Pre	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	30 seconds	Post	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	30 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.248
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	60 seconds	Pre	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	60 seconds	Post	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	60 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.514
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	90 seconds	Pre	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	90 seconds	Post	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	90 seconds	Change Pre-Post	0.181
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	End	Pre	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	End	Post	
Knee, Elbow, Leg, Lower Arm	End	Change Pre-Post	0.055

Table 27: Water 3 Biopulsar Comparisons of Changes between Groups.

Discussion

The BioPulsar showed significant changes in Nose, Hormone system, Immune system, Intestines, Joints, Urinary system, Stomach, and Lung. The BioWell showed significant changes in Brain, Spine,

Coronary Vascular system, Intestines, Urinary system, Hormone System, Immune, and Face. This means that both showed significant changes in Hormone system, Intestines, and Urinary system. Between both devices most important systems showed a significant change.

Conclusion

This study reinforces the previous two studies findings of broad wellness effects with a documented trend toward improved body function. All of the test measures, except the Doppler Laser Perfusion Imager, had at least one change in significance. While the data demonstrates positive changes in organ function in every major body system including brain, heart, kidneys, liver, gallbladder, pancreas, stomach, intestinal track and bladder/pelvic area it should be noted that a larger sample is necessary to confirm any conclusions. A longer test period is also a logical next step to see how these effects either stabilize or change over time.

Acknowledgement

N/A

Statements and Declarations

Ethical Considerations

Human Studies Research Ethics review was provided by NAOEP/IJHC approval 03-30-24-2.

Consent to Participate

All participants signed written informed consent documents.

Consent for Publication

N/A

Declaration of Conflicting Interest

This study was funded using a grant from LifeWave. The authors have no other financial or non-financial conflicts of interest.

Funding Statement

This study was funded using a grant from LifeWave. Grant number GMHC 27.

Data Availability

This data is not being shared in a repository due to concerns about confidentiality.

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